

Studies on Potential Antitubercular Agents. Synthesis of 1-(2'-Morpholino-3'-quinoxalinoyl)-2-benzalhydrazine and 2-Aryl-3-(2'-morpholino-3'-quinoxalimido)-4-thiazolidinones

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Ethyl-2-hydroxyquinoxaline-3-carboxylate with phosphorous oxychloride gave ethyl-2-chloro-quinoxaline-3-carboxylate. This compound upon treatment with morpholine gave ethyl-2-morpholinoquinoxaline-3-carboxylate (A). The ester (A) with hydrazine hydrate (99%) gave the corresponding carboxyhydrazide (B). This carboxyhydrazide when reacted with various aryl aldehyde yielded the corresponding Schiff bases, 1-(3'-quinoxalinoyl-2'-morpholino)-2-benzalhydrazines (1a-g). These Schiff bases were then condensed with thioglycolic acid to give the corresponding substituted-4-thiazolidinones (2a-g), which were screened for antitubercular activity against H₃₇Rv strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*.

THIAZOLIDINONES are well known for their varied spectrum of pharmacological activities¹⁻⁴.

Some of the substituted-thiazolidinones have been found to possess anaesthetic, anticonvulsant, antitubercular and sedative properties^{5,6}. Very recently, pyrazinamide has been found to be highly effective drug for the treatment of tuberculosis. Considering these findings, we felt it is worth synthesising carboxyhydrazide of a substituted-benzopyrazine (i.e. quinoxaline) series, and its various substituted-4-thiazolidinones, and screen these compounds for their antitubercular activity.

The reaction sequence is presented in Scheme 1.

Ethyl-2-chloroquinoxaline-3-carboxylate was prepared according to the reported procedure⁷. This compound upon reaction with morpholine in methanol gave ethyl-2-morpholinoquinoxaline-3-carboxylate (A) in good yields, whose structure was confirmed by ir, nmr and mass spectra. Compound (A) showed a sharp peak at 1720 cm⁻¹ in its ir spectra indicating the presence of an ester carbonyl group. Support for its structure was obtained from ¹H nmr spectra (in CDCl₃), where CH₃ protons are found as triplet at δ 1.4, CH₂ as a quartet at δ 4.45, CH₂ adjacent to N (morpholino) as triplet at δ 3.55, CH₂ adjacent to O as a triplet at δ 3.8 and aromatic protons as a multiplet at δ 7.75.

Ethyl-2-morpholinoquinoxaline-3-carboxylate upon reaction with hydrazine hydrate (99%) gave the corresponding carboxyhydrazide (B) in fairly good yields, whose structure was confirmed by ir, nmr and mass spectra. Compound (B) showed a sharp peak at 1650 (C=O) and 3320 cm⁻¹ (NH) in its ir spectra. Structure of compound (B) was confirmed from ¹H nmr spectra (in CDCl₃), where CH₂ protons (adjacent to N of morpholino group) are found as a triplet at δ 3.5, CH₂ adjacent to O

(morpholino group) as a triplet at δ 3.85, four aromatic protons as multiplet at δ 7.7, NH₂ protons of hydrazide as a singlet at δ 4.05 and NH protons of hydrazide as a singlet at δ 8.6.

This carboxyhydrazide (B) upon reaction with aromatic aldehydes in benzene, gave the corresponding Schiff bases, 1-(3'-quinoxalinoyl-2'-morpholino)-2-benzalhydrazine (1a-g) in good yields.

Schiff bases upon reaction with thioglycolic acid in benzene gave the corresponding substituted-4-thiazolidinone (2a-g) in good yields. A procedure similar to that of Surrey⁸ was followed. Structures of title compounds (1a-g and 2a-g) were confirmed by elemental analysis and spectra. 4-Thiazolidinones showed ir absorption at 1655 (C=O), 1580 (NCO) and 1600 cm⁻¹ (NH). All the thiazolidinones synthesised were screened for antitubercular activity against H₃₇Rv strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*.

The structures of compound 2a and 2f were confirmed by nmr spectra (CDCl₃). Various chemical shift values are as follows.

2a

Compound 2a : δ 2.65 (s) a and b type H, 3.8 (s) c type H, 6.1 (s) d type H, 7.45 and 7.85 (m) e type H, and 9.4 (s) f type H.

Compound 2f: δ 3.4 (s) a and b type H, 3.85 (s) c and d type H, 6.0 (s) e type H, 6.7 (s) f type H, 7.75 (m) g type H, and 9.55 (s) h type H.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were taken on a Perkin-Elmer 633 spectrophotometer. For compounds (A) and (B), nmr spectra were taken on a Varian FT 80 spectrophotometer, and mass spectra on a Varian 114 MAT spectrometer. All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

Ethyl-2-morpholinoquinoxaline-3-carboxylate (A): Diethyl malonate is oxidised with nitrous oxide to give ethyl oxomalonate⁹, which upon condensation with *o*-phenylenediamine gave ethyl-2-hydroxyquinoxaline-3-carboxylate. This compound upon reaction with phosphorous oxychloride gave ethyl-2-chloroquinoxaline-3-carboxylate.

To a methanolic solution of the above crude chloro compound (0.01 mol), morpholine (0.01 mol) was added and the solution was refluxed for 2 h. Solvent was then removed under vacuum and the contents extracted with hot petroleum ether. Petroleum ether extract was concentrated and cooled to 0° with vigorous stirring for 1 h. The crude product obtained was filtered and recrystallised from 70% methanol, (34%), m.p. 66°.

2-Morpholinoquinoxaline-3-carboxyhydrazide (B): Ethyl-2-morpholinoquinoxaline-3-carboxylate (0.01 mol), methanol (50 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (0.015 mol) were refluxed on a water-bath for 8 h. Methanol was then concentrated under vacuum. Reaction mass was cooled to 0° for 1 h and ice-cold water (10 ml) was added with stirring. The solid which separated out was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol, (73%), m.p. 180°.

1-(3'-Quinoxalinoyl-2'-morpholino)-2-benzaldehyde (1a-g): To a solution of 2-morpholinoquinoxaline-3-carboxyhydrazide (0.001 mol) in benzene (200 ml) was added the respective aromatic aldehyde (0.001 mol) and refluxed for 15 h using Dean-Stark water separator. After quantitative water separation, the mixture was concentrated on a water-bath, cooled, filtered, and crystallised from methanol (Table 1).

2-Aryl-3-(2'-morpholinoquinoxalimido)-4-thiazolidinones (2a-g): A mixture 1-(3'-quinoxalinoyl-2'-

morpholino)-2-benzylidenehydrazine (0.001 mol) in dry benzene (200 ml) and thioglycolic acid (0.0012 mol) was heated under reflux for 15 h using Dean-Stark water separator. The solvent was removed

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF 1-(3 QUINOXALINOYL-2'-MORPHOLINO)-2-BENZYLIDENEHYDRAZINE (1a-g)

Compd. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %
1a	C ₆ H ₅	194	92
1b	2-C ₆ H ₄ S	198	94
1c	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	142	92
1d	2-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	202	86
1e	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	164	75
1f	3,4,5-(OCH ₃) ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	219	95
1g	3-(OCH ₃) ₂ -2-(OH)-C ₆ H ₃	204	93

by vacuum distillation and the reaction mixture was cooled and treated with cold saturated sodium bicarbonate solution and filtered. The filtrate was extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 50 ml) to remove the traces of impurities. The bicarbonate extract was cooled to 0° and carefully acidified with cold dilute HCl, till pH 3.0. The solid separated was filtered, washed with cold water and recrystallised from methanol. Similar procedure was employed for the preparation of other substituted-4-thiazolidinones (Table 2).

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF 2-ARYL-3-(2'-MORPHOLINO-QUINOXALIMIDO)-4-THIAZOLIDINONES (2a-g)

Compd. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %
2a	C ₆ H ₅	96	69
2b	2-C ₆ H ₄ S	172	71
2c	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	219	76
2d	2-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	145	76
2e	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	212	72
2f	3,4,5-(OCH ₃) ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	142	52
2g	3-(OCH ₃) ₂ -2-(OH)-C ₆ H ₃	117	60

Antitubercular screening: Various 4-thiazolidinones (2a-g) were screened for antitubercular

activity. *In vitro* antitubercular testing was carried out against the human virulent strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (H₃₇R_v) by the method of disperse culture technique using Kirchner's medium containing Tween-80, as described by Rake *et al.*¹⁰. The tubes were incubated at 37° for 7-8 days and then examined for the presence or absence of the growth of the test organisms. The procedure was repeated with solvent (i.e. dimethylformamide) for control purpose.

Compounds B, 2b, 2c, 2d, 2e and 2f were inactive at 100 µg ml⁻¹ concentration, compound 2a was active at 50 µg ml⁻¹ and compound 2g was active at 6.25 µg ml⁻¹.

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